

Workshop report: Designing a sustainable study profile metadata portal

Co-developed by:

Funded by:

Overview

On 22 July 2025, we hosted a two-hour workshop to engage with stakeholders in the development of a metadata profile for UK Longitudinal Population Studies (LPS).

This profile will be a key output of our work to create a searchable register and integrated information hub for UK LPS - referred as Activity 3 in the Population Research UK (PRUK) [delivery plan](#).

The workshop brought together over 30 participants, including data managers from individual LPS, infrastructure organisations supporting LPS, and funders who enable both the studies and the platforms that facilitate data discovery, access, and sharing.

Aim

A searchable register and UK LPS information hub (Activity 3) meets our objective of enhancing discovery capabilities for LPS. While several metadata and discovery tools already exist, they operate independently, requiring studies to engage with multiple platforms to maintain consistent and up-to-date information. This fragmentation can hinder data discoverability and reuse.

The workshop aimed to gather input on an initial metadata profile that could serve as a common entry point for studies - particularly those not currently represented in existing tools - and support integration across platforms.

Establishing this shared profile is a foundational step towards a more streamlined and connected metadata ecosystem, benefiting both data providers and researchers.

Agenda

13:00 - 13:10: **Welcome & workshop overview** | **Andy Boyd**

Introductions, objectives, and structure of the session

13:10 – 13:20: **Metadata mapping exercise** | **Katharine Evans**

Results of mapping exercise and UK LLC's example of a study profile

13:20 – 13:30: **Metadata tool design and interoperability** | **Chris Orton**

Brief technical presentation on the use of systems and technology needed

13:30 – 13:50: **Group discussion: core functionality & purpose** | **Andy Boyd & Chris Orton**

Whole-group facilitated discussion to explore expectations for how the metadata system should work and be used

13:50 – 14:35: **Breakout sessions: core metadata content**

Smaller breakout groups to define and prioritise core metadata fields required to support interdisciplinary study and data discovery

14:35 – 14:55: **Feedback & synthesis** | **Andy Boyd & Chris Orton**

Groups report back on key points; discussion to highlight commonalities and unresolved issues

14:55 – 15:00: **Next steps & close** - **Chris Orton**

Wrap-up, outline of how input will be used, and next steps for involvement

Speakers & topics

Andy Boyd
PRUK Infrastructure chair
UK Longitudinal Linkage
Collaboration (UK LLC)
Director

Andy Boyd opened the workshop with an overview of PRUK as a new national research initiative to strengthen and connect infrastructure for the UK LPS community.

The session highlighted the importance of high-quality, consistent metadata to improve study visibility and support researchers in finding relevant data. Key challenges include the lack of a universally adopted metadata standard, the burden on studies to maintain multiple profiles across platforms, and limited interoperability between existing tools.

A proposed solution is a unified portal for study data managers to maintain metadata profiles, which would automatically sync with existing discovery systems. This approach aims to reduce duplication, ensure consistency, and enhance the researcher experience.

Katharine Evans
Senior Data Manager at UK
LLC

Katharine Evans presented findings from a metadata mapping exercise that reviewed six UK data catalogues: HDR UK Gateway, CLOSER Discovery, UK Data Archive, Mental Health Data Catalogue, Dementias Platform UK, and the Atlas of Longitudinal Datasets.

The exercise identified common metadata fields used to describe longitudinal population studies, forming the basis for the workshop's group activity to define core and additional metadata content.

Chris Orton
PRUK Technical Lead

Chris Orton provided a technical overview of PRUK's proposed infrastructure investments. He outlined plans for a central, searchable register of UK LPS, designed to improve data discoverability and clarify access routes.

Chris emphasised the importance of integrating metadata across existing platforms. The proposed system would enable automatic synchronisation of study metadata, ensure consistency and enhance the experience for both data managers and researchers.

Insights & takeaways

Attendees were divided across four breakout rooms to explore and prioritise individual metadata fields for inclusion in the proposed PRUK metadata profile tool. Each breakout group was able to broadly agree that the metadata fields presented for discussion should all be included on a profile, however certain information was prioritised as core vs. additional (good to have).

Consensus on metadata fields

Breakout groups broadly agreed that all proposed metadata fields were relevant for inclusion on a profile. Participants distinguished between core fields (essential for discovery) and additional fields (valuable but not critical), helping to shape a prioritised structure for the tool.

Fixed vs variable metadata

There was strong support for including fixed metadata - such as study name, cohort size, age range, and original study purpose - which are straightforward to maintain. However, variable metadata, like access routes or data environments, were also considered essential. Participants emphasised the need for a design that accommodates multiple responses per field to ensure clarity and usability.

Importance of access information

Access details were highlighted as vital, even when studies have multiple hosting arrangements. Clear, structured metadata about access processes will be key to improving discoverability and supporting researchers in navigating complex data landscapes.

Granularity of data collection

Participants stressed the need for metadata that reflects the granularity of data collection, including wave-specific details such as age ranges, collection methods, and demographic coverage. This level of detail is crucial for accurately representing studies with diverse data portfolios.

Additional metadata themes

Suggestions for further metadata elements included:

- Baseline statistics
- Sample characteristics
- Target audiences and scientific focus
- Data usage and access history

These additions could enhance the profile's value and support integration with other discovery platforms.

Metadata standards & interoperability

There was strong support for aligning the profile with existing metadata standards or mappings, to ensure technical compatibility and prevent misclassification across platforms. Consistency in naming conventions and field definitions was seen as essential for interoperability.

Future opportunities: AI integration

Several participants proposed exploring AI-powered search tools, including large language models, to improve cross-platform data discovery. Such tools could offer intuitive, system-wide search capabilities, enhancing access to longitudinal population study data.

Next steps

Insights from the workshop will directly inform the design of the upcoming funding call for our [Activity 3](#).

The proposed metadata profile will be a central component of a suite of tools aimed at improving the visibility, accessibility, and interoperability of metadata for UK LPS.

Key discussion points - such as the adoption of metadata standards, integration of AI-powered search functionality, and inclusion of data use registers and code repositories - will shape the scope and technical direction of the funding call.

These elements are intended to support researchers in identifying relevant studies and understanding their applicability to specific scientific questions.

We'll host a public webinar to introduce this upcoming funding opportunity.

The session will include an overview of the proposed initiative and offer attendees a chance to ask questions and provide feedback.

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